

PROCESSING AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Recent developments have led to a strong interest in the use of cast metal matrix composites (MMCs) in the automotive industry. MMCs are lighter, stiffer, stronger, and more wear resistant than conventional materials and offer greater potential for designing more efficient and durable automotive engine components. Light metal alloys reinforced with relatively inexpensive ceramic fibers are prime candidates for such applications because they can retain their superior properties at higher temperatures. In this investigation a commercially available fiber preform was chosen for fabricating aluminum composites by the high pressure infiltration casting technique (HiPIC). The microstructure of the preforms was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Fully infiltrated composites were made under optimized processing conditions, and were largely free from shrinkage cavities and gas porosity. Optical and scanning electron microscopy were used to characterize the microstructure of the composites. The composites showed higher strength, stiffness, and lower ductility in comparison with the unreinforced matrix alloy cast under identical conditions.

Keywords : Metal matrix composites, composite processing, mechanical properties, elastic property,

1. INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry is currently showing an increasing interest in metal matrix composites (MMCs) that are lighter, stronger, and more wear resistant than conventional materials toward increasing the efficiency and durability of automotive engines. These new materials must retain their superior properties at higher operating temperatures (350 - 450°C) to ensure that the engines meet the stringent economic and environmental demands. Light metal alloys reinforced with ceramic fibers are prime candidates for such applications because they possess many desirable properties. Though metal matrix composites (MMCs) superior properties as compared to monolithic materials, commercial applications of the composite materials have been limited. The first successful application, by the Toyota Motor Company, involved a ceramic fiber reinforced aluminum alloy composite as a piston insert in their 1983 diesel engine¹. More recently, Honda commercially produced a 1990 Prelude engine block using a similar composite in the cylinder wall liner². However, issues such as the high cost of the ceramic fibers, the lack of quality control in the manufacturing process, and the absence of a

design database have limited the commercial exploitation of these potentially attractive materials³.

The recent availability of relatively inexpensive fibers has generated considerable interest in developing MMCs reinforced with ceramic oxide fibers for applications involving high volume production with concurrent cost restrictions, such as required in the automotive industry. Preforms having less well-defined fiber architecture may be used in applications where unidirectional or well defined reinforcement geometries are not necessary. Although the use of such preforms lowers the cost of the precursor materials, the economic advantages may be somewhat offset by the presence of preform flaws such as unfiberized material (shot) or fiber density gradients. A complete elimination of the preform flaws can be prohibitively expensive. Therefore, if the precise effect of these flaws (property or performance degradation, if any) is understood, some of the imperfections might be tolerated in particular applications. Various manufacturing techniques are potential candidates for the production of MMCs in cost sensitive applications. Of these, the technique of infiltrating molten metal into fiber preforms is considered attractive as it offers the potential for fabricating near net shape components. A variation of the infiltration technique, the high infiltration casting (HiPIC), is particularly suitable as it enables the fabrication of composites that have a small grain size, exhibit intimate contact between the fibers and matrix, and are relatively free from porosity⁴. The infiltration kinetics and various mechanical properties of cast composites have been studied by many researchers^{5, 6}. Marked improvements were found in such properties as strength and stiffness, at both room and high temperature, wear resistance and hardness, as compared to conventional materials⁷. The objective of this study is to evaluate the room to elevated temperature mechanical behavior as a function of volume fraction, and the effect of shots on the tensile strength.

2. MATERIALS

The fiber preforms used in this investigation were supplied by the manufacturers (Thermal Ceramics, Augusta GA) in 10, 15 and 20 vol% fiber content. The preform was a rigid, porous solid consisting of an interconnected network of low-cost alumino-silicate fibers with silica binder (less than 5.0 % by weight) added for dimensional stability. Since the characteristics of the preform strongly affect the mechanical properties of the subsequently fabricated composite, it is useful to briefly review the manufacture of the preforms for developing a better understanding of the preform and the flaws inherent to it.

As a first step in the preform manufacturing process, molten alumina-silicate is blown through an orifice, against a stream of hot air, to form the fibers. During the fiber-blowing process, portions of the molten alumina-silicate may not be completely formed into fibers, which results in particulate inclusions (shots) that vary in size from 30 μm to about 250 μm (Figure 1). Shot particles may exist as solid or hollow spheres or ellipsoids depending on whether or not air is trapped within the fibrous material during the blowing process. After the fibers are formed, their lengths are reduced to about 40 - 60 μm . The mixture of shots and fibers is then washed and filtered to separate the shots from the fibers. However, the fibers are not completely free from undesirable shots. Further removal of the shots is possible by repeated cleaning, but with a cost penalty.

The alumina-silicate fibers are subsequently mixed with water and silica binder, and the slurry is vacuum dried into the shape of the preform. After the slurry is compacted to the desired volume fraction and shape, it is fired to form the rigid preform. The preform is then heat-treated at 1260°C for two hours to crystallize the amorphous phase into mullite and cristobalite. The physical and chemical properties of the starting alumina-silicate fibers are presented in Table 1 and the properties of the matrix material (A356) are given in Table 2.

Figure 1. Scanning Electron Micrograph of a 10vol% preform showing a 40µm diameter shot particle

Table 1: Physical and Chemical Properties of fibrous material

PHYSICAL PROPERTIES	VALUES
Fiber Diameter (avg.)	2.2 - 2.7 µm
Fiber Length (avg.)	40 - 60 µm
Specific Gravity, (ASTM C 135)	2560 kg/m ³
Specific Heat 982°C	1088 J/kg°C
Fiber Tensile Strength	1.4 GPa
Fiber Tensile Modulus	117 GPa
Melting Point	1760°C
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	5.6 x 10 ⁻⁶ /°C

3. PROCESSING OF COMPOSITES

High pressure infiltration casting is a method for fabricating particle or fiber reinforced metal matrix composites, where the application of a high pressure forces molten metal into a porous preform. Since the ceramic fibers not wetted by the molten metal, the pressure exerted must exceed a threshold value in order to overcome the surface tension effects and infiltrate the preform. The application of a high pressure during infiltration and solidification also minimizes the occurrence of porosity and shrinkage cavities⁸.

Table 2: Physical Properties of A356 aluminum alloy

PHYSICAL PROPERTIES	VALUES
Liquidus Temperature	615°C
Solidus Temperature	555°C
Coefficient of thermal expansion (20°C to 300°C)	$23.5 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$
Density	2685 kg/ cu. m
Tensile strength	228 MPa
Yield strength	140 MPa
Young's modulus	72.4 GPa
Shear modulus	27.2 GPa
Poisson's ratio	0.33

A 2.54 cm thick preform was preheated at 1000°C for 30 minutes in a furnace before placing it into the die cavity (shown in Figure 2). This was followed by pouring the molten matrix alloy on top of the preform. The total time elapsed between preform placement and metal pouring was approximately 10 seconds. The top punch was then inserted into the die cavity and the ram was lowered onto the top punch to a maximum pressure of 100 MPa. The total elapsed time from metal pouring to the application of pressure was approximately 6 seconds. After about 45 seconds, the pressure was released and the composite was removed from the die.

Figure 2 Schematic of the die used in the HiPIC process to make MMCs

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A quantitative analysis of the fiber distribution in the fabricated composites, performed by Canumalla et al.⁴, indicates that approximately 50% of the fibers lie in the isotropic plane of

the preforms, 10% are oriented at right angles to the isotropic plane, and the rest are distributed at other angles. The fibers are randomly distributed within the isotropic plane, and grains are equiaxed with a size of 15 - 30 μm . The eutectic was found to occur preferentially around the fibers, and that the composite was largely free from porosity or other processing defects. The grain structure and a typical shot particle are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Micrograph of an etched, 10vol% composite showing a solid shot particle and the grain structure

4.1. Elastic Constants

The Young's modulus of the unreinforced alloy and composites with 10, 15 and 20 volume percent fiber measured from room temperature up to 450°C using a dynamic resonance technique⁹, are shown in Figure 4. The Young's modulus of the as-cast alloy decreases by almost 40% with an increase in temperature from 25 to 450°C. As expected, the Young's modulus of the composites increases with increasing fiber volume fraction. The results indicate that the 10, 15, and 20 volume percent fiber composites retain 85 % of their room temperature Young's modulus up to 400°C. The self consistent needle model was used to model the Young's modulus of these composites^{9,10}. The estimated Young's modulus of the composites with completely random fiber orientation was calculated to be 76.9 GPa, 80.0 GPa, and 83.2 GPa, for the 10, 15, and 20 vol%, respectively. These values are slightly lower than the measured in-plane Young's moduli of 79.6 GPa, 86.2 GPa, and 93.4 GPa for the 10, 15, and 20 vol% composites, respectively. This reflects the slightly anisotropic nature of the preforms.

4.2. Tensile Strength and Ductility

The strength of the unreinforced alloy and the 10, 15 and 20 volume percent fiber composites, measured at room temperature in uniaxial tension⁹, are shown in Figure 5. The results show a moderate 10 percent increase in the ultimate tensile strength upon the addition of 10 volume percent fibers. The incorporation of 15 and 20 volume percent fibers show only limited improvement in the ultimate strength, and similar trends have been reported by other researchers^{11, 12}. It is expected that the strengthening effect of the fibers would be more pronounced at a higher temperature¹³, where the matrix material would be relatively softer. Figure 5 shows that the strain to failure of the composites in the present study decreases from 7% for the as-cast alloy down to 1.5% for the as-cast 20 volume % fiber composite. The reduced ductility associated with the presence of the fibers as seen in this study, compares well with other studies¹⁰. This reduced ductility is a critical issue in the structural use of these materials.

Figure 4. Young's modulus of the composite as a function of temperature and volume fraction

Figure 5. Ultimate tensile strength and failure strain of the as-cast composites.

4.3. Fractographic Observations

Figure 6 is a scanning electron micrograph of the fracture surfaces of a 20 volume percent fiber composites tested in tension. The fracture surfaces are rough without indicating any one clear failure origin, and shots are prevalent on both fracture surfaces. These micrographs show mating surfaces of the shots that was presumably intact before failure. This, and the presence of fractured shots a short distance away from the fracture surface indicate that shots play a major role in the failure process. There is no evidence of fiber pullout, as shown in Figure 7, indicating that there is a relatively strong interfacial bonding between the fibers and the matrix.

Figure 6. Scanning Electron Micrograph of a 20 vol% composite showing rough fracture surface and the prevalence of shot on the fracture surface

Figure 7. High magnification view of fracture surface showing the absence of fiber pullout

5. CONCLUSIONS

The fabricated composites are nearly isotropic in terms of their Young's modulus. There is a 10% increase in strength of the composite with a fiber volume fraction of 10%, over the cast matrix. The composites with fiber volume fractions of 15 and 20% show only limited strength improvement over the 10% Vf composite. The ductility of the composites is substantially lower than that of the matrix. The tensile fracture of the composites originates primarily at the shot particles. Reduction of the content of shot particles could improve the ductility of the composites, but with a cost penalty.

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